

SZ-SB-I-04 School transfer to a different state (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090761
ID	SZ-SB-I-04
Title	School transfer to a different state
Educational area	#school
Persona	P: Alvin - Legal guardian https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091406
Short description	Due to Alvin's promotion, the family has to move from Brandenburg to Bavaria, which entails a school transfer for his daughters, Lisa and Lena.
Result	Alvin finds all the necessary information about changing schools through BIRD, registers his daughter Lisa at the new school, and receives confirmation of her enrollment.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Searching for information"• Part 2: "Contacting with the new upper school coordinator"• Part 3: "Applying for the new school"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Alvin is registered at BIRD• Alvin is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder #chat #data-wallet
Services / tools	#BIRD-Calendar

Problem scenario

Introduction

Alvin Weierbach and his family are moving from Brandenburg to Bavaria due to of his new job. His daughters, Lisa (16) and Lena (13), are changing schools in the middle of the school year. Although they will remain in the same grades as in Brandenburg, they will attend different types of schools due to the federal system and the varying educational landscape. Alvin is currently taking care of Lisa's school transfer. He will need to do the same for Lena, who was recently diagnosed with special educational needs. Lisa being 16 naturally wants to have a say in the matter. It is important to Alvin that the school transfer goes smoothly for both daughters.

Problem definition

Due to the different school systems in Brandenburg and Bavaria, the search for a suitable school presents Alvin with a number of bureaucratic hurdles and uncertainties. Gathering all the necessary information, forms and documents and making the necessary considerations and decisions is quite challenging.

Background and context

School systems and curricula vary from state to state. Registering at a new school can be complicated, there are deadlines to meet. Changing schools from Brandenburg to Bavaria is an exciting time not only for Alvin's daughters, but also for him, as he wants the them. With the information he currently has, Alvin does not feel sufficiently informed.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Alvin wants his daughters to be able to start school immediately after the move and hopes that everything will be arranged so they don't have to "sit around" while the formalities are sorted out. He wants a seamless transition and a good start in their new home.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Alvin has received advice from Lisa's current teacher and as a result has already browsed the Bavarian Ministry of Education's website. However, he still feels he lacks sufficient information. He has already searched online for the schools near his new home, but the websites do not answer all his questions and, since the move to Bavaria is still pending, he has not yet been able to visit the schools in person.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Searching for information"

Step 1: Alvin searches in the LearningPathFinder for information about "schools in Bavaria".

Step 2: Alvin finds the page from the [Education server in Bavaria](#) and follows the link to the external website. Alvin reads all the necessary information and explore the school search page for all schools in Bavaria.

Step 3: Alvin returns to the LearningPathFinder and follows the link to "[all types of school in Bavaria](#)".

Step 4: He saves a [digital flyer](#) about the Bavarian school system in his private workspace.

Step 5: Alvin and Lisa open the LearningPathFinder and search for information on the following topics: school authority, procedures for changing schools, possible contact

persons, schools near their new place of residence and types of schools in their new federal state.

Step 6: The LearningPathFinder generates a list of results for schools within a specified radius.

Step 7: Alvin and Lisa save the website of the [Education Authority for the Ebersberg district in Bavaria](#) as a favorite. They find the [form](#) for changing schools and save it in Alvin's workspace in BIRD.

Step 8: Alvin and Lisa follow the Learningpath to the topic "changing schools" ([going to school in Bavaria: The change across state borders](#), [change of school across national borders](#)) and find a suitable educational programme.

Step 9: Alvin and Lisa click through the topic of changing schools.

Step 10: Alvin and Lisa follow the Learningpath on the Bavaria school system and click through [educational offerings](#)

Step 11: Alvin and Lisa are looking for a suitable school near their new home using the [Search and find all schools in Bavaria](#) function.

Step 12: Alvin and Lisa quickly find a suitable school and save the website for future reference, and try to identify potential contacts.

Part 2: "Contacting with the new upper school coordinator"

Step 1: Alvin would like to talk to the new upper school coordinator about his daughter's transfer and get an assessment of Lisa's options. He is very busy at the moment and cannot simply drive to Bavaria, an online appointment is the only option. He received a link from the school to contact the upper school coordinator directly on BIRD and is now writing her a message using BIRD Chat. He requests an appointment to discuss the upcoming move to Bavaria and the change of school.

Step 2: A few hours later, Alvin receives a notification that the upper school coordinator has responded to his message and checks the reply.

Step 3: Alvin books an appointment via the school website and receives a calendar file, which he adds to the BIRD calendar in his workspace to ensure he is reminded.

Step 4: Alvin forwards the BIRD calendar entry to Lisa so she can participate in the conversation.

Step 5: On the day of the appointment, Alvin gets a notification by his calendar. He clicks on the "Join online" button and is directed to the school coordinator's meeting room. The coordinator advises him and Lisa to review information pages about the Bavarian school system, explains how to apply for a new school using BIRD and outlines the required next steps.

Part 3: "Applying for the new school"

Step 1: Alvin and Lisa fill out the forms and applications together and submit them.

Step 2: After some time, Alvin receives a notification in his Data Wallet that the documents have been processed, along with a confirmation of the new school.

Step 3: Alvin confirms his acceptance of the place in writing. He does not need to submit the confirmation to the education authority, as the school handles this on his behalf.